
EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF THE CHANGE OF GEOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS AND THE THEORETICAL ULTIMATE LOAD-CAPACITY OF CORRODED STEEL SAMPLES

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ABSTRACT

It is known that one of the major negative impacts of the corrosion of steel structures is the reduction in geometry. The calculations of the load-bearing capacity of the steel elements depend on the geometric characteristics. The theory confirms that if the geometric characteristics decrease, the load-bearing capacity of the steel elements will also decrease. We conducted an experiment using the S355JR construction steel to determine how the geometry changes. We used electro-chemical accelerated corrosion on which our steel test samples were subjected. We interrupted the electrochemical corrosion process at some point in order to make the necessary measurements regarding the change in geometric characteristics of the test samples. Once we received the experimental data, we processed them using the stochastic method. We also performed theoretical calculations using classical theory and determined the theoretical load-ability (force, bending moment) of our test samples. We have come to the conclusion that the change in geometric characteristics is non-linear and results in a slight decrease in the corrosion of the steel elements, but significantly reduces the theoretical ultimate load-capacity due to corrosion and the corresponding decrease in geometric characteristics.

Key words: : geometrical characteristic, ultimate-load capacity, corrosion.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Corrosion is the process of demolition of steel due to the impact of various aggressive factors (agents) [1]. This is a perfectly natural process [1]. In the case of the operation of buildings and structures, when steel structural elements come into contact with certain substances in the air or water, they undergo a chemical change that reduces the integrity of the steel [1]. This process, as a whole, is called corrosion [1]. Oxygen, sulfur, salt and other materials can also lead to corrosion [1]. When steel is corroded or worsened, it can not bear the necessary impact, as before corrosion [1, 4-17, 21-24]. At some point corrosion can lead to unsafe steel working conditions. Structural steel used in bridges, railways and buildings is subjected to corrosion [1, 4, 24]. Therefore, it is important to monitor and control corrosion in order to avoid emergency [1, 4, 20]. Corrosion alters the surface properties and structure of the surface layer and also reduces the area of the supporting sections [1, 4, 14, 21, 24]. As a result, corrosion directly affects the strength-deformation properties [5-17, 21-24]. When a structure is subjected to mechanical stress after corrosion, it is necessary to investigate the influence that corrosion exerts on the mechanical properties [4-17, 21-24]. Research has shown that corrosion develops to various degrees along the steel elements (Figure 1) [4, 14, 21, 24]. This results in a change in the cross-section depending on the corrosion [4, 21, 24]. The cross-section is the leading factor in carrying out the theoretical calculations of load-ability [2, 3] and its possible change (in length) means that the theoretical calculations will change to the same length [2, 3]. Therefore, it is important to trace how corrosion influences the change in cross-sectional properties [14] of steel and to what extent it reduces, or increases the theoretical ultimate load-capacity of the sections.

Figure 1 Structural steel elements with corrosion, which corrosion is a different on every part of cross-section

2. ACCELERATED CORROSION METHODS

2.1. Salt Spray Method

This method uses a 5 % solution on NaCl (pH 6.5 ÷ 7.2) at a temperature of 35 °C.

The steel samples are placed into the chamber for the salt spray in accordance with the standard ASTM B117-94, or ISO9227:2017 (corrosion tests in arterial atmosphere). When the samples are ready, they are taken out from the chamber, are cleaned up with flowing water and are dried. There follows the removal a corrosive product (oxidized layer from the rust), with a sharp brush. The existence of rust on the oxide layer leads to a loss of weight from the sample. This loss of weight is established by weighing with precision scales before and after the immersion. It is established [15], that the loss of weight is increased in time. The stereoscopic test on a clean surface on a sample shows that after 10 days, using a salt spray

method, there will develop pitting corrosion on the surface. The loss of weight will be around 11 % for a period of 60 days if this method is used.

2.2. Cyclic corrosion testing

It is the most modern and realistic method of accelerated corrosion. A specialized chamber with program control is used which can alternate in complex sequences and combinations the cycles of changing of the different parameters (temperature; humidity; wet / dry; solution concentration; ultraviolet irradiation). It is possible to program various cycles to simulate a variety of operating conditions.

2.3. Scab test

The steel samples are placed outdoors at an angle of 45 °, facing south. They are sprayed with 3 % NaCl solution twice a week. The test continues for about 6 months. The test is standardized (ISO 11474: 2014). This is the easiest method for accelerated corrosion, which also involves wetting / drying cycles, changing of the concentration of the solution, temperature and ultraviolet solar radiation. Although technically easy to perform, this method is labor-intensive and slow, which is why it finds no significant usage in tensile strength tests.

2.4. Immersion in corrosive solution

It is technically the easiest accelerated corrosion to implement. The time to reach the desired degree of corrosion depends on the chemical composition of the solution and on the corrosion resistance of the steel. In [16] natural seawater was used, the experiment lasted for one year and during that time the tensile strength was reduced by 14.5 %. In [17] a 20% solution of NaCl flat test bodies, with a cross-section of 20 × 4 mm, were used. For 8 days, a weight loss of 36 – 55 % was observed, depending on the material used. In general, this method is not preferred by the researchers. Especially in cylindrical steel samples and in solutions close to the natural working environment (i.e. 3.5 % NaCl), the corrosion rate is too small. It is preferable for the process to be accelerated further, usually by-passing electric current through.

2.5. Electrochemical method

The electrochemical method, similarly to the previous one, uses immersion in a corrosive solution, in which case a solution close to the natural working environment (i.e. 5% NaCl) is used. The acceleration is realized via current flowing through steel samples. This leads to anodic dissolution of the steel. The rate of corrosion is directly proportional to the current flowing through the steel sample. For this reason, the galvanostatic method is more often preferable in which the current through the steel sample is stabilized. This eliminates the need for periodic manual adjustments to keep the current constant as its value is maintained by a closed-loop automatic control system. The use of the galvanostatic method makes it possible to make an approximate calculation of the corrosion rate and the treatment time-duration required for obtaining a certain degree of corrosion.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP FOR CORROSION TREATMENT OF THE STEEL SAMPLES

We choose the galvanostatic electrochemical method for accelerated corrosion for this study, as well as other researches [5-13].

We choose a current of 400 mA for each steel sample, where the daily loss of mass (for 24 hours) can be calculated using the Faraday's formula [22]:

$$\eta[\%] = \frac{100 \times M \times I \times t}{W \times z \times F} = \frac{100 \times 56 \times 0.4 \times 24 \times 60 \times 60}{375 \times 2.5 \times 96484} = 2,14 \%, \quad (1)$$

where $t[s]$ – time duration of the treatment, z is the valence of the ferric ion ($z = 2,5$ is the average value for Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions of the corrosion products), $M = 56 \text{ g/mol}$ is the atomic mass of the ferric ion, $W[g]$ is the weight of the steel sample before corrosion treatment, $F = 96484 \text{ C/mol}$ is the Faraday constant, $I[A]$ – electric current through the steel sample.

We use self-developed accelerated corrosion system for the realization of the galvanostatic electrochemical method [24]. This system consists of 50 adjustable current stabilizers with adjustable stabilized current within the range from 16 mA up to 200 mA [23]. This system has the possibility to connect in parallel two or more current stabilizers in order to obtain stabilized current greater than 200 mA (current summation is realized in this case). In order to obtain stabilized current of 400 mA, possible solution is the parallel connection of two current stabilizers, adjusted to stabilized current of 200 mA. We use the same configuration of the system, shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, as in our previous research [23].

Figure 2 Block diagram of the configuration used (two parallel connected current stabilizers to one test sample) of the accelerated corrosion system [23]

Figure 3 (a) Block scheme of the experimental setup [23]; (b) Photograph of the experimental setup

We use a self-developed special holder for steel samples, which we use in previous research [23] in order to ease the process of removing from the solution of the test samples and back returning them into the solution. A photograph of the holder with steel samples is shown in Figure 4a.

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Figure 4 (a) Photograph of the test samples before galvanostatic electrochemical accelerated corrosion method with circle cross-section in parallel length, mounted on the holder; (b) Schedule of one cycle of corrosion development in the cross section of the parallel length of the steel samples

Weight measurements before corrosion treatment and after corrosion treatment and corrosion products removal are performed with precision balance [21-23] KERN model PNJ 600-3M with readability 0.001 g. The graph for the monitoring of the corrosion development in the cross section of the parallel length of the steel samples is shown in Figure 4b. Steel samples are subjected to four such cycles as shown on the cycle in Figure 4b. Information about expectation loss of mass after the treatments, after each cycle and parameters of each cycle, are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Information about expectation loss of mass after the treatments after each cycle and parameters of each cycle

	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3	Cycle 4
Galvanostatic electrochemical accelerated corrosion treatment[h]	216	288	432	504
Remove corrosion products (rust) and measurements of diameter in circle cross-section [h]	48	72	120	144
Number of cycles according schedule	3	4	6	7
Expectation loss of mass [%]	19.26	25.68	38.52	44.94

4. MATERIAL AND BASICS

4.1. Material

We prefer to use in our study structural steel S355JR, as we do [21-24] with the chemical composition according to standard EN 10025-2-2004. We prefer to use steel samples with parallel length $15d$ [2, 21-24]. We divided [23] the parallel length on 30 equal parts (Figure 5) /with step 5 mm/ and made a measurement on diameter with digital caliper with precision 0.01 mm (Figure 6). Before we make a measurement, we remove the corrosion products (rust) in hydrochloric acid - 10 min, in solution of 500 ml hydrochloric acid with 1000 ml distilled water and 3.5g hexamethylenetetramine with temperature 200C, as we do [21-24].

Figure 5 (a) Dimensions of the steel samples [21-24]; (b) Mesh on parallel length

Figure 6 Moments of measurement on diameter in parallel length on steel samples with corrosion

4.2. Basics

According to the classic theory of the strength of materials the stress depends directly on the geometric characteristics of the circle cross-section [2-3] - the formula's:

$$F = \sigma_x \cdot A ; M_y = \sigma_x \cdot W_y ; A = \frac{\pi \cdot d^2}{4} ; W_y = \frac{\pi \cdot d^3}{32} , \tag{2}$$

where: F - load (force); My - bending moment; A – area of cross-section; Wy – section modulus on cross-section; d – diameter of circle cross-section; σ_x – stress. According to our publication [23], we established that for sufficient practical accuracy we may accept for: cycle 1, $\sigma_x = 447$ MPa; cycle 2, $\sigma_x = 445$ MPa; cycle 3, $\sigma_x = 435$ MPa; cycle 4, $\sigma_x = 405$ MPa. The corrosion changes the ultimate tensile strength [23]. The principle is simple, if the diameter of the circle cross-section is changed, that would mean that the ultimate load-capacity would be changed as well.

5. RESULTS

On Figure 7 is present the results on every cycle on galvanostatic electrochemical method, according table 1 of measurement weight.

Figure 7 (a) Cycle 1; (b) Cycle 2; (c) Cycle 3; (d) Cycle 4;

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The changes of the diameter in parallel length is presented on Figure 8 after a process with a stochastic method [18-24].

Figure 8 (a) Cycle 1; (b) Cycle 2; (c) Cycle 3; (d) Cycle 4;

After we have the diameters in every part of parallel length (according to a mesh on figure 5b) we calculate, using classic formulas (Equation 2), the final ultimate load- capacity and the loss of ultimate load-capacity for all the cycles - Figure 9 is for load (force) and Figure 10 is for the bending moment.

Figure 9 (a) Cycle 1; (b) Cycle 2; (c) Cycle 3; (d) Cycle 4

Figure 10 (a) Cycle 1; (b) Cycle 2; (c) Cycle 3; (d) Cycle 4

6. PRACTICAL APPLICATION

In Table 2 the minimum required time in months is calculated, which is necessary to achieve the corresponding corrosion development consistent with our study.

Table 2 Minimum required time of corrosive impact for our study

corrosion category	corrosion rates	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3	Cycle 4
	[mm/year]	[min. month]	[min. month]	[min. month]	[min. month]
C1 (very low)	< 0.0013	14769	24923	46154	54000
C2 (low)	< 0.025	768	1296	2400	2808
C3 (medium)	< 0.05	384	648	1200	1404
C4 (high)	< 0.08	240	405	750	877.5
C5 (very high)	< 0.2	96	162	300	351
CX (extreme)	< 0.7	27	46	86	100

There is a 6-corrosion category of corrosion, depending on the atmosphere, classification by environments aggression, according to standard ISO 9223:2012 (from C1 to C5 and CX) with corrosion rates. Because the values in the standard are for the first year of exposure, we accept that the development of the corrosion rate would be exactly the same as in the rest of the years of the exploitation cycle life of the steel elements.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Our experimental study found that when corrosion was within 20%, change affected the cross-section, the loss of the element of ultimate-load capacity was up to 30% for load (force) and up to 35% for a bending moment, for corrosion category C5 it would take approximately 96 months. As corrosive impact progresses, the loss of ultimate load-capacity reaches 45% for load (force) and up to 60% for a bending moment, for corrosion category C4 it will take an approximately 405 months. With the continued development of corrosion, the impact on geometric characteristics increases and reaches a loss of ultimate-load capacity between 45-

70% for load (force) and within the range of 60-85% for a bending moment, no matter that corrosion has reached only 38% of the weight of the element (for corrosion category C3 it will take approximately 1200 months, or 100 years). When corrosion reaches 45% of the weight of the element, the ultimate load-capacity for load (force) is over 80% and the bending moment is over 90% (for corrosion category C2 and it will take approximately 2808 months, or 234 years). Considering the fact that the material has already the behavior of brittle material [22], it can be unambiguously concluded that if the corrosion is more than 50%, this steel element has no ultimate load-capacity, which would mean that if the corrosion category is CX, that would happen after 8 years of exploitation of the steel element.

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